

Eczema: Etiology, Recovery, and Prevention

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Abstract

This study explored the intersection between modern medical science and the Dharma teachings of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door to address the challenges of intractable diseases, focusing on eczema as a case study. Despite significant advances in medicine, eczema remains incurable, with treatments addressing only its symptoms rather than the root cause. By integrating spiritual perspectives, particularly Master Lu's teachings, this study reveals eczema as a karmic manifestation linked to past actions, such as the killing and consumption of aquatic animals. Case studies demonstrate how karmic debts can be resolved through the recitation of Buddhist scriptures and the practice of compassion, leading to the healing of eczema. Ultimately, this research advocates for a holistic approach to disease, blending scientific understanding with spiritual insight to promote healing and healthy living for humanity.

Keywords: Eczema Etiology; Aquatic Animals; Karma; Spirit; Dharma; Healing

Introduction

Eczema, also known as atopic dermatitis, is a chronic inflammatory skin condition that affects the skin's barrier function, making it more sensitive and vulnerable to environmental irritants. It is characterized by symptoms such as itching, dryness, inflammation, and red or discolored patches, which can range in intensity from mild to severe. Eczema is one of the most prevalent inflammatory skin conditions, marked by recurrent episodes of eczema with varying degrees of erythema, pruritus, xerosis, and pain [1]. In more severe cases, eczema can result in cracked skin or fluid-filled blisters. Although it is more common in children, eczema can affect individuals of all ages.

There is no known cure for eczema, but it is manageable with various treatment options. Dupilumab has been shown to

successfully induce remission of symptoms [2]. Antibody therapies that target inflammatory cytokines or their receptors have demonstrated promising results in preclinical and early clinical studies. These therapies may help reduce healthcare burdens by decreasing the frequency of injections and clinic visits [3]. Although there are numerous treatment options for eczema, their efficacy remains limited [1]. Additionally, group education programs have been found to reduce eczema signs and symptoms over the long term and may also improve quality of life in the short term [4].

However, even with these interventions, flare-ups often reoccur after some time. This suggests that all current treatments, despite technological advancements, are addressing the symptoms rather than the underlying causes of eczema.

At the 4th Davos Declaration on Allergy, scientists emphasized the importance of adopting a holistic approach that integrates research, education, and clinical application to enhance patient outcomes in eczema management [5]. While they considered various institutions and treatments, they did not mention the potential of Dharma practice in the healing process.

We previously reported a case in which eczema was successfully cured through Dharma practice [6]. The patient had suffered from eczema for eight years, seeking treatment from multiple doctors and trying various medications, but with little improvement. After encountering Dharma, his eczema was cured in a short time, and no recurrence has been reported. Since then, no other public cases of eczema cures through this method have been documented in the science community.

In this article, we present new evidence demonstrating that the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is highly effective in curing eczema. Additionally, we provide detailed exploration of the mechanisms behind eczema, the process of recovery, and strategies for prevention.

Etiology

Scientists believe the exact causes of eczema are multifactorial. The pathogenesis involves a combination of genetic predisposition, immune system dysregulation, and environmental factors, with a defective skin barrier playing a central role [3], along with an imbalance in the skin microbiota [7]. Since the 1970s, however, the incidence of eczema in the United States has increased at a rate that genetic drift alone cannot explain, prompting scientists to propose a modern, environmental etiology [8]. Furthermore, some researchers argue that eczema has a complex immunological basis involving Th2 polarization and the release of cytokines such as IL-4, IL-5, IL-13, and IL-31, along with contributions from Th17 and Th22 cells. In chronic lesions, Th1 cells are also implicated [9].

Despite these theories, medical science has yet to provide sufficient evidence to fully support its explanations or offer a curative solution based on its understanding. Currently, there are over 6,000 diseases [6], including eczema, for which no cure exists, largely because their underlying etiology remains undiagnosed by conventional medicine. When a misleading or seemingly plausible theory is applied in practice, treatment is likely to fail. Therefore, exploring alternative dimensions, such as spiritual or holistic approaches, may be crucial in uncovering the root causes of these diseases.

From a Dharma perspective, skin diseases like eczema are seen as karmic in origin. When negative karma is activated, spirits may occupy the patient's skin, manifesting as eczema. These spirits move on the skin, causing discomfort and irritation, which leads to visible symptoms of the condition. Thus, in the Dharma view, the true cause of eczema is spirit occupation. In contrast, the multifactorial causes identified by medical science—such as genetic, immunological, and environmental factors—are regarded merely as secondary symptoms arising from these spiritual influences.

This Dharma perspective is supported through the following six Dharma Question and Answer (Q&A) phone dialogues. In these dialogues, callers ask Dharma Master Jun Hong Lu about the underlying causes of eczema or other skin conditions, and Master Lu offers His insights. The “Wenda” sessions consist of questions and answers, while “Zongshu” sessions involve Master Lu reading the patient's totem, providing a more precise diagnosis of their condition.

A Patient's Eczema Problem [10]

Caller: Hello, Master! A fellow Dharma practitioner, born in 1984, the Year of the Rat, had severe eczema on her chest in 2009. It was painful, and she tried Chinese herbal medicine, bloodletting, and cupping therapy, which placed it under control, though it sometimes recurs. This year, it came back again. Is this a karmic disease?

Master: Yes, it's a typical karmic disease.

Caller: She wants to have a child but is hesitant. How many times of the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* and Little Houses should she recite [6]?

Master: At least three recitations of *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* daily. For Little Houses, she should recite 39 in one set.

Caller: 39 Little Houses, right?

Master: Yes.

Eczema and Scattered Tiny Spirits on Skin [11]

Caller: Master, I apologize for my poor practice. Could you please help me check the quality of my recitations? I was born in 1985, the Year of the Ox.

Master: The quality is okay, and your Little Houses are quite good.

Caller: Thank you, Master. Could you also check on my son, born in 2013, the Year of the Snake? He often has eczema. Does he have any spirits attached to him?

Master: He has many scattered tiny spirits from aquatic animals he consumed in the past.

Caller: How should I perform the recitations for him?

Master: Just continue with your daily practice.

Caller: I recite 49 times of the *Heart Sutra* and 7 times of the *Great Compassion Mantra* for him daily. What other mantras and sutras should I add?

Master: 49 times of the *Heart Sutra* is fine. Also, recite the *Great Compassion Mantra*. How many times do you recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*?

Caller: Twice.

Master: Increase it to three and recite 27 times of the *Xiao Zai Ji Xiang Shen Zhou*.

Caller: Got it. He also does his own daily recitations and has started reciting Little Houses.

Master: Good.

Sea Animal Consumption Causing Acne and Eczema [12]

Caller: Hello, Master! A fellow Buddhist practitioner used to eat a lot of live aquatic animals but has now switched to a vegetarian diet. He recites the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* 49 times daily, but recently, he developed acne on his face and eczema on his hands. How many Little Houses should he recite for this?

Master: Consuming aquatic animals in the past doesn't mean karma disappears after practicing Buddhism; the retribution will still manifest eventually. The solution is straightforward: recite Little Houses along with the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra*.

Caller: How many Little Houses should he recite specifically for this issue?

Master: He should recite 7 Little Houses at a time until the condition improves.

Caller: Does he need to perform a large number of *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* self-cultivation recitations?

Master: No. It's not necessary.

Caller: Is 49 recitations of the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* daily enough?

Master: Yes, it's fine.

Lifelong Skin Disease Problem [13]

Caller: Hello, Master! A child has had a skin condition from a young age, scratching until the skin is raw. Should we focus more on reciting Little Houses or *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra*, or do both?

Master: Both are necessary. Skin diseases are often related to past karma involving the consumption of aquatic animals or killing aquatic creatures, as well as the mother eating too many aquatic creatures during pregnancy. In Chinese medicine, it's believed that consuming aquatic creatures can activate latent conditions, causing skin bumps and infections to surface. If the mother consumes too many aquatic animals during pregnancy, the child's skin will likely suffer.

Caller: So, we should strengthen the recitation of *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* and also recite Little Houses, correct?

Master: Yes.

Caller: Should the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* be included in daily recitations or as part of a large self-cultivation sheet?

Master: It's better to include it in the daily recitations.

Eczema in Children Caused by Mother's Consumption of Aquatic Animals [14]

Caller: Hello, Master! Can you help me look at a child born in

2016, the Year of the Monkey? He sometimes has eczema on his body.

Master: He has eczema on his back and thighs.

Caller: Yes, that's correct.

Master: It's because of the consumption of too many aquatic animals.

Caller: This child was a vegetarian in the womb.

Master: His mother did, don't you understand?

Caller: How many Little Houses should be recited for the child's karmic creditors?

Master: Let me see... quite a few. At least 560 Little Houses. By the time you reach around 300, you will see significant improvement.

Caller: His eczema is not very severe right now.

Master: You need to take this seriously. If left untreated, it could spread and become difficult to manage.

Caller: He has had eczema since he was just over a month old.

Master: Yes, you should be cautious.

The Karma Behind Eczema in a Vegetarian Baby [15]

Caller: Master, does a vegetarian baby's eczema result from the karma of eating live creatures in a past life?

Master: Yes, skin diseases are caused by consuming live creatures.

Caller: Should he recite the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* for this?

Master: Yes.

The six dialogues revolve around cases of eczema and other skin conditions, primarily caused by karmic retribution from past actions, particularly the consumption of live aquatic animals. In each case, Master Lu advises reciting Buddhist scriptures, especially the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*, the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra*, and Little Houses to address karmic debts. He emphasizes the importance of consistent practice to alleviate both physical symptoms and underlying spiritual causes.

To investigate the validity of this theory, we analyze 9 cases-2 presented in the main text and 7 in the supplemental section-to assess whether practicing Buddhism can significantly improve or even cure eczema and related conditions.

Results

Case 1: My Son's Eczema and Pollen Allergy Are Cured via Dharma

In 2014, our family was full of joy when my son was born. However, when he was only about 2 months old, his head and face were covered with eczema, with small red rashes all over. We had to put herbs on his skin during the day, but his condition did not improve.

We took him to see a Japanese pediatrician. The doctor said that the child was still young and that many of the symptoms would disappear when he was a bit older, around 6 months. Hearing this, I felt a lot more at ease. However, by the time he was 6 months old, the skin disease had not only failed to heal but also spread to the limbs and even the whole body. The thighs, the roots of the thighs, the knees, and the arms were especially bloody and scaly, with red marks and scabs mixed together, itching and hurting.

Whenever he felt itching, he scratched hard. During the day, adults could watch the child and help him pat the itchy area to prevent him from scratching. But at night, he could not sleep and kept scratching. When I heard the sound of my child scratching his skin, my heart broke and I thought, "When will my child get better?"

We had to take him to a dermatologist because he could not be treated in the pediatric department. The doctor prescribed oral medication and ointments containing hormones in order for the child to sleep well at night. I knew that these drugs had certain side effects. However, as long as we could make his body not itchy and let him fall asleep peacefully, we had to use them! In the end, we applied the medicine as directed by the doctor. During the medication period, he did not itch much so did not scratch much and was able to sleep peacefully at night.

However, these drugs only treat the symptoms, never addressing the underlying cause, and the child must use a hormone cream consistently. In summer, since he sweats more, he is more likely to commit skin diseases, so a hormone cream has become an essential product. In Japan, this disease is called "atopic dermatitis", and there is no specific medicine effective for it in hospitals.

At age 3, he was diagnosed with hay fever, making a bad situation even worse. Every year from January to April, he had a blocked nose, itchy eyes, tears and sneezing. He could not stop rubbing his eyes with his hands, causing his eyes and the skin nearby to be red and swollen. In Japan, hay fever is a national epidemic disease, so it is not surprising. However, as a mother, I blamed myself for my child getting this disease at such a young age. I felt that I had not done a good job as a mother, and I was very upset that my child had to suffer like this. Every year we took him to the hospital regularly so that the doctor could prescribe him oral medication, nose spray and eye medication.

My son was supposed to grow up innocent and carefree, but he grew up with all kinds of medications and pain! Looking at my poor child, I could do nothing but silently pray for a miracle to occur, so that he could have a healthy body and a happy childhood without drugs!

I am grateful to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Bodhisattva for blessing me with access to the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door.

After studying Dharma, I knew the cause and effect. It turned out that my child had skin diseases from childhood because I ate too many live sea animals during my pregnancy, and the karmic consequences of my killing harmed the next generation-my son. This is all my own sinful karma. Who can I blame?

After studying Dharma, I knew that my child would be saved,

my heart was full of hope, and I was no longer worried about his illness. I firmly believe in the words of Master Lu that "there is a solution if there is Dharma!" Wow power generates motivation. I determined to practise the Three Golden Buddhist Practices of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door to help my child [6]. I believed that Guan Yin Bodhisattva would bless my child!

I did my homework by daily reciting the *Great Compassion Mantra* 3 times, 7 times, 27 times and now 59 times; the *Heart Sutra* 3 times, 7 times, 27 times and now 59 times; the *Eighty-eight Buddhas Great Repentance Text* 3 times, and now 5 times; *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* 21-108 times; *Xiao Zai Ji Xiang Shen Zhou* 49 times; *Cundi Dharani* 21 times, *Qi Fo Mie Zui Zhen Yan* 21 times, and *Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots* all 49 times.

After I finished my daily recitation, I helped my son with his recitation. At the beginning, I helped him to recite the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* 49 times a day. Three months later, I made 3 vows to Guan Yin Bodhisattva:

- (1) Help my child recite the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* 10,000 times within one month.
- (2) Recite 7, 21 and 49 Little Houses per set, set by set, for my child's karmic creditors.
- (3) Release two sets of fish for my son, 500 fish per set (I don't remember exactly the time it took to complete. However, both were completed on time).

Additionally, on the first day and fifteenth day of every lunar month or the celebrating days of Buddha and Bodhisattva, I will release beings for myself and my child.

I can't remember exactly how many Little Houses I have recited and how many fish I have released. With time, I found that I had become healthier physically and mentally, and my son's illness had rapidly improved. This strengthened my belief in the Dharma that is infinitely powerful, and that practising Buddhism will definitely change our destiny! I am grateful to Guan Yin Bodhisattva for Her compassionate blessing and to Master Lu for His compassionate blessing.

For both myself and my family, I continued practising the Four Golden Buddhist practices, making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, performing life liberation, and studying *Buddhism in Plain Terms* to eliminate karma and pay off karmic debts [6].

One year later, when my son was 5, a miracle did occur! His stubborn skin disease, eczema, was completely cured (Figure 1). He finally got rid of the illness afflicted and started a happy new life! Now I have enrolled my son in swimming classes, and he can finally swim in the water without worrying about his skin condition! What's even more amazing is that my son's hay fever, which had been incurable for a long time, has unknowingly disappeared!

Guan Yin Bodhisattva is so merciful! The Four Golden Buddhist Practices are true and not false! My son has finally ended his days of living with skin diseases and hay fever, creating a medical miracle! Gratitude to merciful Guan Yin Bodhisattva! Gratitude to benefactor, Master Jun Hong Lu! (Figure 1).

Figure 1: My son fully recovered from eczema after I practiced Buddhism. (A) Before I encountered Buddhism, his face was covered with red spots. (B) After I practiced Buddhism, his face became completely clear, with no spots remaining.

One person practising Buddhism, the whole family benefits! Before I practised Buddhism, my daughter cried in the middle night quite often. Since I practised Buddhism and recited Buddhist scriptures, my daughter has stopped crying and fussing at night. When my mother had a small stroke, I helped her to recite Buddhist scriptures, make vows, release living beings, and also transferred my merits and virtues of reciting *Buddhism in Plain Terms* to her. Her small stroke was surprisingly healed without seeing the doctor. I also helped my husband eliminate his bad karma and improve his relationship with his supervisor.

In 2021, I made 4 great vows:

- (1) Always follow Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master Jun Hong Lu to cultivate my mind and behavior.
- (2) Respect the teacher and respect his teachings.
- (3) Devote myself to one Buddhist practice, and never quit.
- (4) Help more sentient beings to be free from suffering and gain happiness in order to repay the kindness of the Buddha!

We must cherish one of the last Dharma ships in the Age of Dharma Decline and be sure to get on board!

Dharma practitioner: C51

Comments: Eczema alone is already a tough condition for doctors to treat, let alone when combined with pollen allergies. Through practicing Buddhism and reciting scriptures, the mother was able to cure her child of two illnesses that are considered incurable in medical terms [16]. This once again proves the authenticity and effectiveness of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door.

The healing of the pollen allergy also supports the conclusion we previously reached regarding asthma: when karmic obstacles are eliminated, the trigger will lose its triggering effect [17]. In this case, the pollen lost its ability to trigger the allergy.

Case 2: Eczema Afflicting Me for over 40 Years Was Cured by Practicing Buddhism

I would like to share with you my story of curing the skin

disease eczema that has afflicted me for more than 40 years in just 3.5 years by practising the Four Golden Buddhist Practices of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door:

- (1) Make vows.
- (2) Recite Buddhist scriptures (sutras and mantras).
- (3) Perform life liberation.
- (4) Read *Buddhism in Plain Terms*.

I hope that my experience will allow me to make good affinity with innumerable sentient beings and transform countless sentient beings to practise Buddhism!

Forty years of stubborn skin disease brought me endless miserable and torment

I was born in 1974. Not long after I was born, my parents noticed my skin was weird. The skin on my face and body first faded, blistered and then festered a little bit. The festering started from a point to a piece and finally resulted in my inability to be held by my parents.

My parents took me to all the major hospitals and doctors, and it was diagnosed as eczema. The condition is recurring, stubborn, unable to be cured, and is treatable only with a few common medicines in case of an emergency. When it was severe, my whole body was covered with small blisters that itched so much that I scratched desperately. My parents had to use gloves to wrap my hands all over. I couldn't sleep well at night, I had no strength during the day, I grew up yellow and skinny, and my skin was always covered with ointment.

My mother heard someone say that eating snakes could cure eczema. After I ate twice, I had more attacks so she gave up. However, terrible bad karma was created.

When I was 38 years old, I had a full-blown skin disease. My palms, the backs of my hands and face itched like crazy. I felt like something was crawling on my hands (after studying Buddhism, I realized that this was retribution for eating snakes), and the only

way to relieve the itching was to scratch and bleed and then rinse the wound with tap water. A senior dermatology professor looked at my medical history and said: "The skin disease is still severe at your age and you will carry it for life."

I was desperate after years of eczema plague. Many times, I cried from my heart: "Who can save me?" "Who can free me from the torture of this disease?"

I was fortunate to encounter Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, and the eczema was improved

It must be the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva who heard my cry and came to save me! Under the guidance of Guan Yin Bodhisattva, I was fortunate to meet Dharma practitioner S in February 2016 at my newly hired workplace. She said that my skin disease could be relieved by practising the Three Golden Buddhist Practices of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door: making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, and performing life liberation.

I was very interested in hearing that. Practitioner S then offered me the *Buddhist Recitation Collection* (Buddhist scriptures), *Introduction to the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, A Guide to Reciting Little Houses* and *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, a tape recorder and other Dharma information for free. I felt as if I had found a gem. That day, I learned to recite the *Great Compassion Mantra* during my break. When I got home from work, I immediately opened the books and read them one by one. When I saw the real cases published in the book, I felt immense joy and hope. I felt like I had found a therapeutic solution to my illness!

Early the next morning at 5:00, I was awakened by a loud knock on the door and stepped out to see no one was there. This must be the Dharma Protector reminding me to get up early and recite Buddhist scriptures. It took me a short time to learn to recite Buddhist scriptures and the Little Houses.

After practising Buddhism for more than two months, practitioner S took me to liberate fish, and then we went to senior practitioner P's home for a group study of *Buddhism in Plain Terms*. Practitioner P said, it is imperative for a reciter to be a vegetarian, or the quality of Buddhist scriptures recited will be compromised. I immediately offered Bodhisattva incense in front of the Buddhist altar at P's home. I made a vow to be a vegetarian from now on and forever.

In June 2016, practitioners S and D-S helped me set up the Buddhist altar at my home. I made a vow to liberate lives on the first and fifteenth day of every month of the lunar year. Every day, after offering Bodhisattva incense, I felt especially Dharma joy when I sat in front of the Buddhist altar to recite Buddhist scriptures. I recited the Little Houses quickly. Every day, I have the Great Compassion Water to drink. I can sleep more soundly at night, and I wake up less often with itchy skin in the middle of the night. My physique is obviously better than before.

I kept listening to Master Lu's recorded Dharma talks, reading *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, and repaying my karmic creditors with Little Houses. I swabbed the itchy areas on my face and hands with

Great Compassion Water. I also dreamed that Master Lu came to me to bless me in my dreams, which was particularly Dharma joyful.

After a few months, the itchy skin on my face and hands improved greatly, and my skin glowed. My body has changed qualitatively from the inside out. It was as if I was being transformed into a new person. The practitioners who know me are also happy for me when they see my skin improving.

By making great vows and performing more merits and virtues my eczema was cured

In 2017, I was 43, entering the age of predestined 369 calamity [6]. In May, my karma broke out. The skin disease on my hands flared up again, resulting in an unbearable itching. I tossed and turned at night and couldn't sleep. I wondered: "Did I do something wrong?"

One day, practitioner P told me that she dreamed that I was the owner of a sea animal store in my past life. After hearing this news, I was frozen. Why had I chosen to kill instead of another profession in my previous life? It was terrible! What huge karma it created! The evil cause of killing in my past life has caused skin disease in my present life since birth. The money, fame and fortune from past lives could not be carried to this life, but only the karma never leaves my soul, just as Master Lu enlightened in *Buddhism in Plain Terms*: "Nothing can be brought away, only the karma that follows."

When added the karma of eating snakes while I was a student, which made my life worse than death. Like the Dharma saying: "You create your own karma and suffer the consequences." I apologize for my evil deeds, and I deeply repent to you, Guan Yin Bodhisattva!

During that time, I experienced karmic obstacles that hindered all aspects of my life. My interpersonal interactions were also very difficult, and I was ostracized everywhere. I felt devastated. I resigned from my job and decided to concentrate on reciting Buddhist scriptures at home and keeping liberating lives.

It was because of Guan Yin Bodhisattva's mercy that I was fortunate to meet practitioner T when I accepted Dharma gems. T told me, "This is because you lack powerful vows, insufficient merits and virtues. You should conduct more merits and virtues. Make a vow to release more beings according to your financial capability. I realized then that I had not done enough good deeds and merits to resist the onset of killing karma. My karma broke again because of this.

That night, I made four big vows in front of Guan Yin Bodhisattva:

(1) Release fish under slaughter every day of that month, rain or shine.

(2) Pay my karmic creditors 7 Little Houses every day.

(3) Convince sentient beings to practise Buddhism, offer people Buddhist books whenever I meet them, and show them how to practise Buddhism and recite Buddhist scriptures.

(4) Recite 3 times *Eighty-eight Buddhas Great Repentance* daily to specifically eliminate skin karma.

Within that period I was very productive and relaxing, and Buddhist scriptures were recited very smoothly. The most joyous thing was that the skin on my hands was getting better day by day and the skin ulcers were completely under control. It's amazing how much improvement there is in just one month! They did not itch anymore at night and I could sleep comfortably.

A month later, practitioner S helped me find a job where I could recite Buddhist scriptures during work. A warm current swept through my heart and I could not stop crying. I felt so happy and grateful, a feeling I had never experienced before in my life. Please accept my deepest gratitude to Guan Yin Bodhisattva for Her merciful saving!

The Four Golden Buddhist Practices, making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, performing life liberation, and reading *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, are truly efficacious! The Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva is so merciful, letting me encounter such a wonderful Dharma Door at my most difficult time. The compassionate benefactor, Master Jun Hong Lu, gave me hope. I was saved by the Dharma and deeply touched by the selfless and altruistic spirit of my benefactor. I was spurred on by His sincere teachings.

Practitioners are not bonded by blood relationships, but our

relationships are superior. Hence, I have no reason to be lazy and recessive in Buddhism. I am not afraid of difficulties. With the presence of the Guan Yin Bodhisattva, everything will be fine as long as I recite Buddhist scriptures and pay off my debts.

By December 2019, three and a half years had passed. I have recited a total of 3,500 Little Houses for my karmic creditors, released more than 40,000 lives specifically for skin illness, insisted on reading *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, and would often calm down to read *Buddhism in Plain Terms* in detail so that I could understand deeply and thoroughly the true meanings, kept on listening to Master Lu's programs every day, such as Q&As, and also watched videos of Dharma conventions regularly. I felt particularly full of Dharma joy.

In the process of listening to and reading *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, I have collected some valuable contents that have played a significant role when giving alms to sentient beings, and certainly have helped me a lot in my own Buddhism journey. By performing the Four Golden Buddhist Practices, I have completely recovered from the stubborn skin disease that has afflicted me for over 40 years (Figure 2). My sincere gratitude goes out to the Great Guan Yin Bodhisattva! I am so grateful to Master Lu, who saved me from eczema torment and suffering for over 40 years!

Figure 2: Practicing Buddhism completely healed my eczema. (A) Before encountering Buddhism, my right hand was covered with eczema. (B) After practicing Buddhism, my right hand fully recovered from eczema.

I am grateful to the great Guan Yin Bodhisattva for bringing such a marvelous Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door into this world. I am also grateful for practicing such a wonderful Dharma Door. In this life, I am lucky to have followed the benefactor Master Jun Hong Lu, to cultivate my mind and behaviors. His wise teachings led me, the ignorant who was lost in the Saha world, to be converted so I could find my way home. Once again, I am grateful to the great Guan Yin Bodhisattva.

I hope that my presentation can wake up your inner Buddha nature, help all sentient beings awaken, be free from suffering and attain happiness.

Dharma practitioner: Y52

Comments: The Dharma embodies right faith and right thoughts, in contrast to deluded thoughts and wrong intentions. For example, Buddhism teaches against killing and eating animal meat, which aligns with righteous faith and right thoughts, whereas believing that killing and consuming animal meat can cure diseases stems from deluded thoughts and wrong intentions. Such delusions carry serious consequences. In this case, her mother killed a snake and let her eat its meat, believing it would heal her eczema, but this act, rooted in deluded thoughts, only worsened her condition.

Her experience serves as a lesson to those who doubt the existence of the spiritual world—she could not see the snake spirit but could feel it moving within her body.

Recovery and Prevention

In the above section on etiology, Master Lu, in His responses to callers' questions, mentioned methods for recovering from eczema, even though the focus was primarily on the causes of eczema. Below are three Q&A sessions that specifically address how to treat eczema. The last one, in particular, also discusses how to prevent eczema.

Vegetarian Baby with Severe Eczema and Restlessness at Night due to Family Karma [18]

Caller: Hello, Master! A boy born in 2017, the Year of the Rooster, is a vegetarian baby. Could you please check his health condition and see if he has any spirits? Recently, he has been very restless.

Master: He has spirits on him.

Caller: He becomes especially restless at night. He's eight months old and still refuses to eat solid food. Since six months old, he has developed round patches of eczema, which keep recurring.

Master: I can see many crabs. This is troublesome; it's related to the karma of his mother's family. They need to sincerely recite the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra*.

Caller: How many times should they recite the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra*?

Master: Start with 74 times.

Caller: Recite 74 times daily, right?

Master: Yes, for one week. Let's see if it improves.

Caller: How many Little Houses are needed?

Master: Not too many, 68 Little Houses.

Caller: Got it. How many fish should be released?

Master: About 1,080 fish should be released.

Caller: Understood. Is there anything else we should pay attention to?

Master: Not much else. The main thing is to help him eliminate his karmic obstacles, particularly the scattered tiny spirits from the crabs and fish. They must be ascended; otherwise, the condition won't improve.

Caller: Got it, thank you, Master.

Adjusting the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* Recitations According to One's Condition [19]

Caller: Hello, Master! You previously mentioned that the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* shouldn't be recited 49 times continuously for months and should be reduced after some time. When I reduced it to 27 times and recited for one month, I developed eczema on my hands, and I sometimes got pimples on

my scalp. I feel like I shouldn't reduce the recitations.

Master: Then don't reduce them.

Caller: So it's fine to keep reciting 49 times?

Master: Of course! For normal situations, yes, but in special cases like yours, you should adjust according to your condition. It's like how people take one pill a day under normal circumstances, but if your condition is more serious, a doctor may prescribe two pills. This is something you need to understand.

Caller: Yes, I used to kill a lot of animals and eat sea animals.

Master: It was too many—I see that you ate crabs.

Caller: So, I'll adjust the number of recitations based on my body's response.

Master: Exactly.

Issues Related to Skin Diseases [20]

Caller: Hello, Master Lu! The child has congenital eczema. Is this a karmic disease, and how should parents perform recitations for it?

Master: Skin diseases are generally karmic diseases, especially congenital ones, which are mostly due to significant karmic debts from past lives or ancestors. For treatment, you need to recite the *Great Compassion Mantra* 21 or 49 times daily and pray to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva to cure the skin disease.

Recite the *Heart Sutra* 7 or more times daily to ask for wisdom.

Recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* 3 times daily to repent and eliminate the karmic obstacles causing the skin disease.

If you or your family members killed or ate live animals, or if the mother consumed too many aquatic animals during pregnancy, it could affect the child. You need to recite the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* 21, 27, or 49 times daily for 3 months to ascend these tiny spirits. It is also essential to make a vow to stop eating or killing live creatures.

In addition, recite at least 3 Little Houses per week dedicated to the child's karmic creditors.

Lastly, make vows, release animals, and vow not to consume or kill living beings in the future.

You can also apply Great Compassion Water to the affected areas daily.

Discussion

When compared to other life-threatening diseases, such as asthma [17], brain disorder [21], cancer [22], and genetic disease [23], eczema might seem less serious since it is not fatal. However, it can severely disrupt daily life, leading to sleeplessness, fatigue, and a decline in mood [24]. Despite being a relatively minor condition, eczema remains incurable, even after hundreds of years of

medical research. In fact, eczema, like any of the over 6,000 known intractable diseases [6], continues to resist a true cure, highlighting the limitations of modern medicine in fully understanding its underlying causes.

Without a clear understanding of its true cause, developing treatments that address the root of the condition remains elusive. As a result, current medications can only manage its symptoms, much like cutting grass. After trimming the blades, the grass may appear to be gone, but without removing the roots, it inevitably grows back. Similarly, treatments for eczema provide temporary relief, but the condition recurs.

When confronted with unresolved medical challenges, modern medicine often approaches from two perspectives: internally, focusing on genetics; and externally, focusing on the environment. Research indicates that boys inherit a higher genetic predisposition for certain conditions, and factors such as premature birth and low birth weight make children more susceptible to developing eczema [25]. The use of antibiotics and living in humid environments can increase the risk of eczema in children [25]. In East Greenland, the high prevalence of eczema in adults is attributed to the cold climate, along with unique genetic and environmental factors [26]. Additionally, environmental factors such as physical surroundings, human activities, nutrition, and biogenic influences are believed to play a significant role in the development of eczema [27].

If viewed purely from a scientific perspective, the design of these experiments, the investigations, and the analysis of the results all follow scientific logic, so the outcomes should be correct. However, from a higher perspective, the truth may not necessarily be as it seems.

From a Buddhist perspective, the genetic influence on the occurrence of eczema is merely a manifestation of collective karma. If parents enjoy eating live fish and shrimp, how could their children's bowls be free of fish and shrimp? The act of eating live fish and shrimp leads to eczema in the parents, and similarly, it causes eczema in their children. The karmic obstacles created by the parents' act of killing naturally manifest in their children due to the effects of collective karma [6].

The environmental influence on eczema is also indirect. For instance, 69% of individuals aged 18-78 years in Tasiilaq, East Greenland, showed visible signs of current skin disease, and 82% (242/295) were diagnosed with dermatoses [26]. What do those residents rely on for their livelihood? The answer is well-known worldwide! Naturally, skin diseases are rampant there. If the local residents don't change their lifestyle and dietary habits, moving to the equator wouldn't lower the high incidence of their skin diseases. Thus, the environment is merely a trigger that ignites the karmic obstacles. Without karmic obstacles, the environment would not cause eczema. This has been discussed in our previous report in asthma [17].

Since the 1970s, the incidence of eczema in the United States has risen sharply, and medical science attributes this to environmental factors [8]. However, when we examine the occurrence of eczema

alongside fish consumption, a clear pattern emerges. Data on U.S. consumption of total fishery products, measured in pounds per capita per year from 1909 to 2018, reveal that between 1909 and 1964, over 55 years, consumption fluctuated between 8.7 and 10.5 pounds per capita annually [28]. From 1964 to 1990, however, within just 26 years, consumption steadily rose from 10.5 to 15.6 pounds per capita per year, marking a 48.6% increase (Note: the year cited may not be 100% accurate). The surge in eczema cases in the U.S. since the 1970s is closely tied to this increase in the consumption of aquatic animals. So, why look for other factors behind the rising incidence of skin diseases in the U.S. since the 1970s? Every bite of meat carries karmic consequences, and when retribution arrives, one must personally bear the results [6].

Due to the lack of a true understanding of the causes of eczema, all the treatment methods developed are aimed at alleviating symptoms, such as medication [29], phototherapy [30], psychological therapy [31], etc.

This situation underscores the limitations of our knowledge and understanding of the true nature of the illness world. However, when we shift to viewing the world through the lens of Dharma, an entirely new perspective emerges. As Master Lu has enlightened us, skin diseases are karmic in nature, often manifesting as tiny spirits occupying the surface of the skin. The successful treatment of eczema in 10 cases [6] (Case 1-2, Case S1-S7) serves as compelling evidence supporting Master Lu's teachings and the authenticity of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door.

Where does karma come from? It originates from past lives (Case 2), from ancestors (Case S4, Q&A 7), wrongful deeds committed in youth (Q&A 2, 3, Case S3, S4, S6, S7), and even the mother [6] (Q&A 4, 5, Case 1, S1), among other sources. Of all activities that generate karma, killing is the most significant contributor [6].

Interestingly, curing eczema through practicing Dharma often appears to be more efficient than treating conditions like Alzheimer's disease (AD) [21], cancer [22], and genetic disorders [23]. For instance, when patient N1's wife completed reciting 49 Little Houses for his karmic creditors, his eczema was healed [6]. Similar outcomes were observed in this study (Case S1, S2, S3, S6, S7). However, Case 2 presented a different scenario. In her past life, she operated a sea animal business, and this karmic debt manifested as eczema after birth in this life, resulting in over 40 years of suffering. Even after encountering Buddhism, it took her 3.5 years of diligent practice to fully dissolve her karma. Diseases rooted in past-life karma, such as genetic disorders [23], are typically more difficult to cure. Her case exemplifies Master Lu's teaching: "When we leave this human world, we take with us nothing but our karma."

The spirits of aquatic animals, being smaller and simpler in nature, have relatively straightforward souls. Unlike the spirits of larger animals or humans, which often harbor more complex and vengeful minds, these smaller spirits are more willing to ascend when given the opportunity, such as reincarnating as larger animals in their next life. When they depart from the human body, conditions like skin diseases tend to naturally heal, similar to ailments such as

asthma [17], AD [21], cancer [22], and other persistent diseases [6]. This illustrates the basic mechanism by which the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door addresses eczema. From theory to practice, this has consistently proven to be effective [6].

Eczema symptoms are often more severe at night [32] (Q&A 7). Science medicine attributes this to peripheral and central circadian rhythms, increased inflammation, heightened sensitivity to allergens, and bacterial factors. However, from a Dharma perspective, there is another explanation: while sentient beings in the Human Realm are active during the day, those in the Ghost Realm are active at night [33]. The tiny spirits of aquatic animals residing on the skin belong to the Ghost Realm, and they become more active at night, exacerbating symptoms.

The cases in the current study further deepen our understanding of the intractable diseases. This understanding compels us to reconsider the belief that killing and consuming aquatic animals for nutrition comes without consequences. In fact, the harm from killing and eating aquatic animals far outweighs the benefits. Engaging in these acts is akin to “drinking poison to quench thirst”. When retribution comes, it will be too late for regret. If humans seek animal protein or fat, there are plant- and algae-based alternatives [34-36].

Medical science emphasizes integrative treatment approaches, including mind-body therapies, for managing eczema [37], which is a positive development. However, medical science’s inability to fully comprehend the underlying mechanisms of skin diseases leaves many treatments feeling like “scratching an itch through a boot.” One might wonder why, after hundreds of years, the true cause of eczema remains undiscovered. Firstly, karma and spirits are invisible to direct human observation [6, 21]. Secondly, the time lag between cause and effect complicates the matter. For example, in cases of human killing, immediate consequences like arrest prevent widespread violence. Similarly, killing fish may lead to skin diseases, but the delayed effects make it difficult to directly link actions to consequences. Understanding these karmic effects is not only a sacred task for Buddhists but for all sentient beings, as it provides a health concept that benefits all of humanity.

The pursuit of beauty is innate to human nature. Achieving healthy, beautiful skin is neither complex nor difficult: it begins with abstaining from acts of killing and adopting a vegetarian or vegan lifestyle.

Supplemental Cases

Case S1: A Newborn’s Persistent Eczema Was Quickly Cured by Practicing the Four Golden Buddhist Practices

Previously, my family had worshiped Guan Yin Bodhisattva and the God of Wealth. However, it was only after practicing Buddhism that I realized that simply worshiping without reciting Buddhist scriptures is equivalent to not practicing Buddhism at all, as it shows a lack of true understanding of Buddhist teachings. I am deeply grateful to Guan Yin Bodhisattva for guiding me to a fellow practitioner, who led me into Buddhism and taught me the principle

that everything has karmic causes and effects. Practicing Buddhism and reciting Buddhist scriptures has greatly benefited both my family and me, and I’d like to share one of the several miraculous experiences.

Half a month after my granddaughter was born, she developed eczema. It spread all over her body after her first month. Applying eczema cream helped a bit, but it never fully healed and kept recurring. Seeing her suffer made my heart ache. When my daughter-in-law returned to work after maternity leave, I was the one taking care of the baby. Watching my granddaughter’s eczema worsen, I remembered the Buddhist books that a fellow practitioner had kindly given me. After reading through the Buddhist materials, I discovered the root cause of the child’s eczema: the mother had consumed too many living creatures during pregnancy, which led to the baby developing eczema before she was even one month old.

I immediately made a vow in front of Guan Yin Bodhisattva to eat vegetarian meals twice a month. To my surprise, the very next day, my granddaughter’s eczema subsided.

Later, because I didn’t strictly observe my vow and Buddhist precepts, her eczema returned.

With the help of a fellow Buddhist practitioner, I began to apply the “Four Golden Buddhist Practices” that Master Lu had taught us-making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, performing life liberation, and reading Buddhism in Plain Terms. I vowed to:

1. Release 1,200 fish in total.
2. Recite 21 Little Houses for the child’s karmic creditors.
3. Read one chapter of *Buddhism in Plain Terms* every day.
4. Recite the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* 10,000 times in 100 days for her.

I prayed Guan Yin Bodhisattva for healing the child’s eczema and recovering health.

My power of a vow surpasses her force of karma. With the fulfilment of these vows, within 3 months, her eczema was completely gone. I am so grateful to Guan Yin Bodhisattva!

Dharma practitioner: Z53

Case S2: The Compassionate Bodhisattva Healed My Child’s Eczema Through My Dharma Practice

I have three sons: the eldest is 14 years old, the second is 13, and the youngest is 9.

My second son was born in 2010 with eczema. It was due to his eczema that I found my way into Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door.

Every year, during the Christmas and New Year period, my son’s eczema would worsen, spreading from head to toe, and oozing uncontrollably. Applying moisturizer only caused his skin to crack, and he couldn’t sleep well at night. I sought both Chinese and Western medical treatments, but the doctors said eczema is just like this, which left me very anxious.

In 2012, I searched the internet extensively for treatment methods. By chance, I came across a post introducing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. I thought to myself, "I'll give it a try, even if it seems like a long shot."

I called the 20R Australia Oriental Radio, and the practitioner who answered taught me how to perform daily recitations and how to recite Little Houses.

Following the instructions from the practitioner at 20R Australia Oriental Radio, I made a vow to help my son by reciting 49 Little Houses in batches and praying to Guan Yin Bodhisattva for the improvement of his eczema. As I recited the Little Houses one batch after another, about a month and a half later, by the time I had finished the first set of 49 Little Houses, my son's severe eczema gradually improved and has never recurred since.

My son's illness became a catalyst for my deeper commitment to Buddhism, leading me to the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, where I discovered the Dharma that would benefit me for life. Since then, I have embarked on the path of practicing Buddhism! I am immensely grateful to Guan Yin Bodhisattva!

Fellow practitioner: H54

Case S3: Miraculous Recovery from Severe Eczema after Ascending Small Spirits on My Body by Reciting the Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots

I remember when I was young, I would go frog-catching and snail-hunting after school, unknowingly accumulating a lot of killing karma. When I first started reciting Buddhist scriptures, I wasn't at a very high level of status of mind. I simply wanted to help ascend the frogs and snails I had once harmed.

A few days after I began reciting Buddhist scriptures, I dreamt of Master Lu. In the dream, I wanted Him to read my totem, but He seemed busy and left without talking to me. In the dream, it felt like I just wanted Master to know that I had started reciting Buddhist scriptures!

After some time of reciting Buddhist scriptures, one day while I was reciting the *Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots* and washing dishes in the kitchen, I suddenly felt warmth in the middle of my forehead, between my eyebrows, and then I smelled sandalwood incense. At that time, I hadn't even set up a Buddhist altar in my home. Later, I realized that it must have been the Bodhisattva coming to bless me! This greatly strengthened my faith in practicing Buddhism because I knew that Bodhisattva was watching over us at all times!

Shortly after I began reciting Buddhist scriptures, I noticed that I had developed a dense rash of eczema from my chest down to my navel. At first, I thought it was caused by dirty bedding, so I aired my blankets under the sun, but the rash didn't improve. I went to the hospital, took medication, and applied ointments, but nothing worked, and the condition dragged on for more than a year.

One day, I saw a fellow practitioner's sharing on Master's blog, and her symptoms were similar to mine. From her story, I learned that eczema is caused by small spirits on the body and can only

be cured by reciting Buddhist scriptures to help ascend them. I immediately made a vow to Guan Yin Bodhisattva to recite the *Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots* 108 times daily for six months to help ascend these small spirits.

By the fifth month, all the eczema had disappeared, leaving only scars.

By the end of the year, the scars were completely gone.

I knew then that all the small spirits on my body had been successfully ascended!

Shared by: L55

Case S4: Eating Live Animals Since Childhood Led to Severe Eczema, Recovered After Practicing Buddhism

Buddhist practitioner D's father often went fishing in a small river when she was a child, and the family regularly consumed fish and shrimp, taking countless lives. Later, her father slaughtered pigs, which led to karmic retribution manifesting in the next generation. Several siblings in the family suffered from skin problems-indeed, karma never fails!

Before practicing Buddhism, she had severe eczema on her hands, and one of her fingernails was nearly rotten. Over time, the eczema spread to other parts of her body, becoming red, swollen, and constantly oozing pus. She also developed shingles, all related to skin issues. Master Lu once mentioned that skin diseases often result from karma associated with killing and consuming live aquatic animals.

Later, she developed rhinitis, which made it impossible to use fans, and air conditioning, or endure cold drafts, leading to frequent conflicts at home. Rhinitis caused her to rely on mouth-breathing. She eventually acquired bronchitis. Overwhelmed by numerous health issues, she was deeply distressed.

After discovering Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door and reading the books, she realized that her illnesses were karmic retribution. She repented for her past misdeeds, including abortion, consuming live water animals, and engaging in sexual misconduct. She also understood why her health was poor, her career stagnated, and her gynecological issues persisted, along with her child's health problems and marital discord. The burden of negative karma was simply too heavy. She began daily recitations of the *Great Compassion Mantra*, *Heart Sutra*, *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra*, and *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*, and she burned Little Houses to help her karmic creditors.

One night, she dreamt of climbing out of a river. Her body was covered in holes oozing pus. It was terrifying. In the dream, she felt despair and wanted to end her life. As she jumped, the hand of Guan Yin Bodhisattva caught her. In the dream, she cried uncontrollably, waking up in tears, filled with deep regret for all her wrongdoings, and immense gratitude for the Bodhisattva's salvation. She vowed to be a lifelong vegetarian.

During the process of offering Little Houses for her karmic creditors, she dreamt of her aborted child, who appeared pitiful

and hungry, taking money from her wallet. Eventually, she dreamt that the child had successfully ascended. Once, she even dreamt of Ji Gong Bodhisattva pressing acupuncture points on her back. Afterward, He said, "Your gynecological issues are gone; I've blessed you." The Bodhisattvas are truly compassionate.

After practicing recitations, her rhinitis healed without medication, her bronchitis never recurred, and the eczema on her skin disappeared after reciting the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra*. The redness and swelling were gone. Little Houses and the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* were incredibly effective!

Within about six months of practicing, all the ailments that had plagued her vanished.

Sincerity brings results, and with diligent practice, the Bodhisattvas will bless and protect us.

Fellow Dharma practitioner: N56

Case S5: Incerely Reciting the Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance Healed Over a Decade of Eczema

Every year from April to June, my hands would break out in eczema, and I couldn't use laundry detergent or dish soap. If I did, the skin on my hands would crack, causing unbearable pain. This went on for more than ten years, and it was very painful.

In the first volume of *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, chapter 2, "Refrain from All Evil, Practice All Good", Master Lu taught: that after reciting the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*, the merits and virtues from reciting it can be used to eliminate small karmic obstacles. If those obstacles become activated and manifest as spirits, it's because the karmic burden is too deep and heavy, and even after chanting, they may still be activated. Then, Little Houses are needed to help these spirits ascend, which can be a painful process. Out of compassion, Guan Yin Bodhisattva teaches us to recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* to eliminate these small karmic obstacles before they manifest as spirits. This scripture is truly wonderful, as it connects with the spiritual energy of heaven and earth.

From April 15 onwards, I began reciting the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* 21 times daily for about 10 days. At the same time, I recited over 100 times the *Great Compassion Mantra* each day to enhance my energy, and I continued my regular recitations and burning of Little Houses for my karmic creditors. Then, a miracle happened-my eczema completely healed!

After washing my clothes, my skin no longer cracked or hurt. My long-standing issue disappeared completely! I am so grateful to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva! The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is incredibly effective, and Guan Yin Bodhisattva responds to all who call upon Her.

I vow to practice diligently in this lifetime, never to regress, and to repay the kindness of the Buddhas and my master.

I hope my sharing inspires those still hesitating to have faith in practicing Buddhism, recite Buddhist scriptures, repay karmic

debts, and find peace and happiness!

Practitioner: L57

Case S6: Miraculous Recovery from Eczema that Troubled Me for 7 Years After Just Over a Month of Practicing Buddhism

On September 13, 2017, I experienced immense physical and emotional trauma, which caused me to develop acute eczema. My skin became red, swollen, and oozed pus. The unbearable itching and thickened skin constantly flared up. I used specialized eczema creams and herbal medicines, which only provided temporary relief but never cured the condition. This continued for over seven years, with each summer bringing the torment of eczema.

In mid-November 2022, I was fortunate to meet Buddhist practitioner S, who introduced me to the benefits of practicing Buddhism. She later invited me to her home and generously gave me many Dharma Gems. However, when I returned home and saw the Buddhist scriptures like the *Great Compassion Mantra* and the *Heart Sutra*, I foolishly thought they would be difficult to recite and put aside.

It wasn't until 2024 that I reconnected with practitioner S. She asked if I had started reciting Buddhist scriptures and how my progress was. I sent her pictures of the two books, saying that they were well-kept. Under her guidance, I began my daily recitations according to Master Lu's teachings. Later, I met practitioner Z, who consistently encouraged me. Knowing I found the recitations challenging, she kindly provided me with a sutra player and other Dharma Gems. I'm deeply grateful to both of them.

On February 9, 2024, I officially began my recitations. On February 25, I visited practitioner S's home with Z. They encouraged me, saying that the beginning is always difficult, but if I continue diligently, it will get easier. I shared with them a dream I had that morning, where someone replaced the black blood in my body with red blood and removed two black objects from my stomach. They told me this was an auspicious dream. On our way home, one of them asked with concern, "Are you in good health?" I replied, "Yes, I'm fine. I walk 10,000 to 20,000 steps a day." However, I even did not think about my eczema at the time.

Around March 15, while reciting Buddhist scriptures, I noticed the eczema returning. My skin became red and swollen, and I scratched it until it bled. When I squeezed the affected areas, yellow fluid oozed out. Red, swollen patches appeared on my legs and arms, with more yellow fluid seeping out. By April 15, the skin on my arm began to peel, and more yellow fluid came out.

However, by May, without me even noticing, the eczema had quietly healed. This was the time of year it usually flared up, but this time, I was cured. It was only then that I recalled the dream from February 25.

During this period, I recited approximately 50-60 and my wife recited around 100 Little Houses for our aborted child. We also recited for the deceased. Reflecting on this, I realize that without the blessings of the Buddhas and Bodhisattvas, how could I have

recovered so quickly? I am deeply grateful for Guan Yin Bodhisattva's compassion and my master for bringing this wonderful Dharma Door to the Human Realm! As I continue practicing Buddhism and reciting Buddhist scriptures, I have experienced many miracles, which have strengthened my faith in the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. My resolve has grown stronger, and I am more diligent on the path of cultivation. My wife is also moved and says we must continue practicing with unwavering faith.

I hope that fellow practitioners who have received the Buddhist scriptures will cherish their connection to Buddhism, seize the opportunity to recite scriptures and realize that the Bodhisattvas' compassionate salvation is true and not illusory. I am also very grateful for the encouragement and help from my fellow practitioners.

Dharma practitioner: L58

Case S7: Healing 8 Years of Eczema in 2 Months by Reciting Buddhist Scriptures

In the summer of 2022, I was fortunate enough to come across Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. At that time, I was receiving therapy at a wellness center to remove dampness from my body, and it was there that I met a fellow Buddhist practitioner. She spoke to me about Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, and I felt especially drawn to it. She asked me, "Would you like to learn?" I said, "Yes, I would." So, she gave me a red book of the *Buddhist Recitation Collection* to recite.

However, I wasn't very diligent at first. I would recite when I had time, and when I was busy, I wouldn't. My work kept me busy, so I could only recite on my way home from work.

Perhaps my karmic obstacles were too deep because, while reciting, I felt like my mind was so full that I couldn't take in a single verse. It was extremely difficult for me to learn. When I first started learning to recite the *Great Compassion Mantra*, it took me several days to learn the first line. I couldn't memorize it, and each time I finished reciting, I couldn't remember the next verse. During that time, I watched some of Master Lu's Dharma talks and learned to pray to Guan Yin Bodhisattva. So I prayed for Her to bless me so that I could quickly memorize the scriptures.

Perhaps I was too eager and impatient. I remember clearly that once when I was praying to Guan Yin Bodhisattva to help me memorize the scriptures quickly, I thought of Master Lu's teaching, "Just focus on sowing the seeds and don't worry about the harvest." This phrase has stayed with me ever since, and I constantly use it to encourage myself to persist in learning Buddhism and cultivating my mind.

From that point on, I began to put in more effort. Whenever I had free time, I would use it to study and recite the scriptures. At first, I didn't understand how to recite Little Houses. After asking a senior practitioner, I realized that I needed to first complete my daily recitations and then begin reciting Little Houses. I began doing my daily recitations in November 2022 and started reciting Little Houses. At first, I didn't specifically recite Little Houses for

my eczema. I began by reciting 21 Little Houses for the karmic creditor of my house. Then, to help liberate aborted children, I recited another 21 Little Houses. Additionally, I had suffered from back pain for over 40 years, so I focused on healing that first, and I didn't prioritize the eczema.

Strangely enough, since I started reciting Little Houses, the atmosphere in my home has become much more harmonious. My child, who used to be rebellious, has become filial and understanding.

As to my eczema, it had persisted for about 7-8 years. In the early years, it was quite mild. Every summer, when it got hot, it would flare up, and by winter, it would subside. When it appeared, I would apply some ointment, and it would go away. For those few years, this approach worked. Whenever I heard of a good treatment, I would buy the medicine and apply it. The symptoms were mild, so they always went away after applying the ointment.

However, starting in 2020, my eczema became severe. It started small but gradually spread all over my lower legs, covering large areas. At its worst, the rashes looked like big, red, swollen pimples, covering large patches. The hotter it got, the more they itched. I couldn't help but scratch, which caused pain when the skin broke. That entire summer was unbearable. Only those who have experienced it can truly understand. I couldn't sleep well at night. Even when I managed to fall asleep, I would scratch unconsciously, waking up to continue scratching, causing my skin to break. My entire pajama pants would be stained with blood.

When the eczema was severe, I sought hospital treatment. Initially, it helped, but after a while, I kept applying ointments without improvement. I then began searching for alternative treatments. Upon hearing of a good remedy, I traveled over 350 kilometers to buy medicine from a well-regarded traditional Chinese doctor. The first dose of medicine relieved my symptoms, but since the affected area was large, the medicine ran out in less than a month. I ordered a second dose by mail. It worked initially, but eventually lost its effect, and I gave up.

My eczema became so severe that the skin between my legs became swollen and broken. Walking was painful, and I had to rest at home.

Master Lu once mentioned that skin diseases are mostly related to killing karma. Indeed, this was true for me. I had run a restaurant for two years and sold fish for some time. Karma follows us like a shadow—there's no escape. The negative causes we create must be endured as negative consequences.

I am extremely grateful to Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master Lu for bringing such a wonderful Dharma Door to the human world, giving me a chance to repent for my past wrongdoings and repay my karmic debts. In 2023, I began reciting Little Houses to eliminate the karmic debts related to my eczema.

After the New Year, I recited 21 Little Houses, and the eczema subsided. It wasn't as widespread as in previous years, and only a few spots appeared. I had only vowed to recite 21 Little Houses for

my karmic creditors and had not yet released any fish, the eczema already improved so quickly, with just a few remaining traces.

Fearing another severe flare-up, in May 2023, I made the following vows to Guan Yin Bodhisattva:

1. Become a lifelong vegetarian.
2. Recite 49 Little Houses for my karmic creditors.
3. Release 600 fish.
4. Share my experience once my eczema is healed to help more sentient beings.

I vowed to complete these vows within 3 months. I diligently fulfilled them. Remembering the suffering caused by the itching in the past, I was terrified of relapse and used every moment to recite Buddhist scriptures. Gratitude to the compassionate blessings of Bodhisattva, my eczema began to heal. From large patches, it reduced to just two spots. While the spots decreased, the itch was still unbearable, and at times, I wished I could cut off the skin to stop the itching. By the end of July, I could see the scars gradually healing. When I was close to fulfilling my vows, the eczema was completely gone!

I am truly grateful to Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master Lu! The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is incredibly effective. In just about two months, by making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, and performing life liberation, I repented for my past mistakes, and I eliminated karmic debts. Bodhisattva compassionately blessed me. All I feel is gratitude, endless gratitude!

Through learning Buddhism and reciting scriptures, I completely cured my eight-year-long eczema without spending a penny. Words cannot express my gratitude. Every time I think of it, tears fill my eyes. I am deeply grateful to Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master Lu for ending my long years of suffering in such a short time!

I often listen to Master Lu's Dharma talks, and I've learned that all karmic illnesses can be resolved through making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, and life liberation. Hearing other practitioners' stories of how they healed through these practices strengthened my faith. When it hadn't happened to me, I treated these stories as mere tales. But when it actually happened to me, the feeling and experience were beyond words.

I want to encourage those who have not yet practiced Buddhism, those who haven't recited Buddhist scriptures, or those who doubt the power of the Dharma: Whoever practices Buddhism will benefit; the earlier you learn, the sooner you will benefit. When you don't practice, you remain unaware of Dharma's wonders. Once you start learning Buddhism and reciting scriptures, things will improve, your life will become smoother, and you'll be filled with Dharma joy!

In less than a year, in just nine months, the blessings have been continuous. For a newcomer like me, the results have been so remarkable-imagine the experiences of senior practitioners!

Sometimes I think I'm unfortunate for not learning earlier. If I had started sooner, I wouldn't have suffered so much.

Fellow Dharma practitioner: L59

Conclusion

Through the examination of eczema from both scientific and spiritual perspectives, this study reveals the complexity of understanding and addressing intractable diseases. Despite the significant advancements in medical research, eczema remains an incurable condition. The failure to fully understand its root causes highlights the limitations of modern science, which tends to focus primarily on genetics and environmental factors, often offering only symptom-based treatments. The recurring nature of eczema suggests that the current medical model falls short of addressing the deeper causes of such conditions.

In contrast, the Dharma perspective, particularly through Master Lu's teachings, offers a broader view that integrates the spiritual dimension into understanding disease. Eczema is seen as a karmic manifestation, often caused by the spirits of aquatic animals attached to the human body. These spirits, occupying the skin's surface, are linked to past actions such as the killing and consumption of animals. Case studies within the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door practice have demonstrated successful healing through the recitation of Buddhist scriptures and the practice of compassion and non-harm. This approach addresses the karmic debt, resulting in the spirits' departure and, subsequently, the healing of physical symptoms.

The karmic consequences of killing animals, especially aquatic creatures, are profound, and the suffering they cause can manifest in the human body as disease. The practice of non-harm, including adopting a vegetarian or vegan lifestyle, not only alleviates karmic burdens but also promotes health and harmony for future generations.

In conclusion, this exploration of eczema underscores the need for a more holistic approach to disease, one that transcends the material world and incorporates Dharma wisdom. By understanding the karmic roots of illness and practicing spiritual living, we can find not only relief from physical ailments but also deeper spiritual peace and insight. The synergy between science and Dharma offers a comprehensive path to healing, both physically and spiritually, paving the way for a more harmonious existence for all beings.

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Ethical Statement

The author was not involved in any aspect of the experimental design, treatments, or result analysis for these patients. All experimental procedures and practices carried out by the patients, their mother, or other relatives were done independently.

Statements

The 9 cases and 9 Q&As in the text were translated from Chinese to English based on their intended meaning rather than a word-for-word approach. The remaining portions of the paper were written based on my limited understanding of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. If there are any inaccuracies or deviations from the true meaning of the Chinese version, or if the content does not accurately reflect Master Lu's teachings, I sincerely seek forgiveness from the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva, all Buddhas and Bodhisattvas, Dharma Protectors, and Master Jun Hong Lu.

Disclaimer of Liability

The contents of the presentation, comments, and discussion, including text, images, and other information obtained from Dharma practitioners, are provided strictly for reference purposes. Due to the unique nature of individual karma, results similar to those experienced by the practitioners may not be replicated. The experiences and advice shared should not be construed as medical advice or a diagnosis.

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Conflict of Interest

No.

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